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EVALUATION OF SOME PLANT ORIGIN CHEMOSTERILANTS TO CONTROL COCKROACH POPULATIONS

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ABSTRACT:

The extracts derived from mature seeds of *Ocimum basilicum*, *Butea monosperma* and *Gynandrosis gynandra*, flowers of *Butea monosperma* and rhizome of *Acorus calamus* were evaluated for reducing offsprings against different species of cockroach viz. *Periplaneta Americana*, *Blatella germanica* and *Supella supellectilium*. In the present study, the various extracts (rhizome, flowers and seeds) were assessed by mixing the suspensions as well as powdered plant materials with the diet. Cockroaches were fed on these treated diets from the newly moulted adult stages. The extracts of *Acorus calamus*, *Butea monosperma* and *Ocimum basilicum* proved very effective to control the population of cockroach. In all the cases, the extracts showed higher percent of sterility (81-100%) against *Americana*, *Blatella germanica* and *Supella supellectilium* except *Ocimum basilicum* and *Gynandrosis gynandra* which were ineffective to check the growth of the cockroach. This study indicates the potential of extracts to be used as an alternative in developing and producing chemosterilants as an effective measure used in controlling and eradicating the cockroach population.

KEYWORDS: Chemosterilant, Nymph, *Ocimum basilicum*, *Butea monosperma* and *Gynandrosis gynandra*

INTRODUCTION:

A great horde of the world's first insects explored into the carboniferous forests. They seized the broad opportunity for living offered by the great expansion of greenery, proliferating with astonishing diversity. There were creatures like today's dragonfly, except that their bodies were 15 inches long and they had a wing span 30 inches. But most successful crawler and flyer was-----as still is in twenty first century A.D. ---- the Cockroach. In that ancient time the Earth's surface swarmed with no fewer than 800 species. (Tillyard 1937, Rehn 1945) At the present time there are about 3500 species mostly of tropical origin and perhaps as many more which have not been named or described.

Today the pest cockroaches have manmade environment highly suitable for their existence. Where ever food is stored, manufactured or handled cockroaches are potentially capable of establishing an infestation.

The number of contributions to the scientific literature on cockroaches has grown steadily since 1900. A number of books, leaflets, and collected works have appeared to through light on the biology and physiology of cockroaches (Marlet 1908, Sein 1923, Fullon 1928, Gould and Deay 1940, Back 1937, Chamberlin 1949, Roth and Willis 1954, 1957, 1960, Rehn 1951, McKittrick 1964, Cameron 1961, Cornwell 1968, Bennett 1977, Bell and Adiyodi 1982.

Amongst the more important contributions made on the biology of American cockroach are those of Sein (1923) in Puerto Rico; Von Fischer, (1928) in Germany, Nigam(1933) in India; Gould and Deay (1938 a&b) in the United States.

Blattella germanica is usually found in hotels, kitchen and public houses (Zabinski 1929) and in large number in city dumps in New York(Felt 1926, Porte 1930, Chamberlin 1949), The occurrence of the German cockroach has increased recently in the private house also (Berthold and Wilson 1967) . The contributions on the biology of *Blattella germanica* are due to studies of Haber (1919), Woodruff (1938), Wille (1933), Gould 1941, Rau (1944) Gerber (1950), Willis et.al. (1958) , Ogata (1976).

We are benefitted by the research works of a number of scientists on brown banded cockroach (Saussure 1864, Shaw1924, Whelan 1929, Back 1937 a &b and Prat 1955, Kevan and Chopard, 1954, Mallis 1954, Hafez and Affifi1956 and Willis et.al.1958

Control of cockroach populations (Ebeling and Reiersen 1969, 1973, Gupta et.al. 1973, Bajomi and Elek1974, Chadwick and shaw1974, Engelbrechet 1976, Bennet and Lung1977)

A pilot survey was done in the present study on the evaluation of chemosterilant properties of some plant materials. The flowers and seeds of *Butea monosperma* (flame of the forest) and rhizome of *Acorus calmus* proved to bring about reduced fertility (Firdaus Rana et al, IJRPC2012, 2(4)). These plant materials in some way check the ovarian maturation and formation of egg capsules in the three cockroach species viz. *Periplaneta Americana*, *Blattella germanica* and *Supella supellectilium*. In the present study it was not possible to isolate the active principle responsible for the disruption of normal egg maturation process. A number of proteolytic and lipolytic enzymes have been reported from the seeds and flowers of *Butea monosperma* (IJPSN-17-07-11 MAZUMDAR) Occurrence of similar types of enzymes are also expected in *Acorus calmus* as the rhizome of *Acorus calmus* has been found to check the ovarian development in *Dysdercus*. These enzymes must be disrupting the yolk deposition process in cockroaches to cause the production of less number of fertile egg capsules.

A more detailed of the constituents of these plant materials and their action mechanism would greatly help in developing some useful chemosterilants which could be used to control the ever increasing populations of cockroach in human establishments.

Materials and Methods:

Mature seeds of *Ocimum basilicum*, *Butea monosperma* and *Gynandrosis gynandra*, flowers of *Butea monosperma* and rhizome of *Acorus calmus* were air dried in the shade, plant materials were extracted using petroleum ether (b.p.40-60°C)as solvent. Suspensions of these extracts at 0.5% and 1% were prepared in water using 5% benzene as solvent.

In the experiments, the chemosterilant of various extracts were assessed by mixing the suspensions as well as powdered plant materials with the diet. Cockroaches were fed on these treated diets from the newly moulted adult stages. The control experiment, in which cockroaches were fed with the untreated food of the same quality, was also run simultaneously for the comparison. All treatments were replicated thrice. The insects were observed for:

1. The number of fertile capsules produced by the females.
2. The number of nymphs emerging out per fertile capsule.

OBSERVATION:

The results of this study are presented in the tables 7.1, 7.2, and 7.3. From these tables; this can be observed that both flowers and seeds of *Butea monosperma* and the rhizome of *Acorus calmus* proved very effective. The number of egg capsules produced per female was quite less in all the three

Table 7.1 Evaluation of some plant origin chemosterilants *Periplaneta Americana*

S. N.	Plant material	%mixed with the diet	Number of capsules produced	Number of fertile capsules produced	Number of Nymphs emerged from each fertile capsule
1.	Ocimum basilicum seeds	0.5	46	44	15
		1.0	46	45	14
2.	Butea monosperma seeds	0.5	12	02	04
		1.0	08	02	03
3.	Butea monosperma flowers	0.5	16	04	06
		1.0	14	04	05
4.	Gynandropsis gynandra seeds	0.5	45	44	14
		1.0	46	43	12
5.	Acorus calmus rhizome	0.5	12	04	04
		1.0	10	05	04
6.	Control		48	46	15

ANOVA FOR DATA ON FERTILE CAPSULES PRODUCED

S.N.	Source	DF	SS	M S	F	Table F 1% level
1.	Plant materials	05	15407	3081.4	489.1	5.64
2.	Replicates	02	29.4	14.33	2.33	2.56
3.	Error (a)	10	63	6.3		
4.	Doses	01	0.1	0.1	0.07	9.3
5.	Plant material Vs. doses	05	2.9	0.6	0.42	5.06
6.	Error (b)	12	17	1.4		

ANOVA FOR DATA ON NYMPHS EMERGED

S.N.	Source Error (a)	DF	SS	MS	F	Table 'F' 1% Level
1.	Plant materials	05	815.3	103.6	33.4	5.64
2.	Replicates	02	18.1	9.0	2.9	2.56
3.	Error (a)	10	31	3.1		
4.	Doses	01	0.5	0.5	0.35	9.3
5.	Plant materials Vs. doses	05	4.6	0.92	0.65	5.06
6.	Error (b)	12	17	1.4		

Table 7.2 Evaluation of some plant origin chemosterilants *Blatella germanica*

S.N.	Plant material	% mixed with the diet	Number of Capsules produced	Number of Fertile Capsules produced	Number of Nymphs Emerged From each Fertile capsule
1.	Ocimum basilicum seeds	0.5	05	04	28
		1.0	05	04	26
2.	Butea monosperma	0.5	02	02	12
		1.0	02	01	08
3.	Butea monosperma flowers	0.5	03	02	14
		1.0	02	01	10
4.	Gynandropsis gynandra seeds	0.5	04	03	26
		1.0	05	04	26
5.	Acorus calmus rhizome	0.5	03	01	12
		1.0	03	01	12
6.	Control		05	05	28

ANOVA FOR DATA ON FERTILE CAPSULES PRODUCED

S. N.	Source	DF	SS	MS	F	Table 'F' 1% Level
1.	Plant materials	05	82	16.4	27.3	5.64
2.	Replicates	02	01	0.5	0.83	2.56
3.	Error (a)	10	06	0.6		
4.	Doses	01	0.4	0.4	0.28	9.3
5.	Plant materials Vs. doses	05	06	1.2	0.85	5.06
6.	Error (b)	12	17	1.4		

ANOVA FOR DATA ON NYMPHS EMERGED

S.N.	Source	DF	SS	MS	F	Table 'F' 1% Level
1.	Plant materials	05	2205	441	18.45	5.64
2.	Replicates	02	60.6	30.3	1.26	2.56
3.	Error (a)	10	239.4	23.9		
4.	Doses	01	21.7	21.7	15.5	9.3
5.	Plant material Vs. doses	05	52.7	10.5	7.5	5.06
6.	Error (b)	10	17	1.4		

Table 7.3 Evaluation of some plant origin chemosterilants Supell supellectilium

S.N.	Plant material	%mixed With the diet	Number of Capsules produced	Number of Fertile capsules produced	Number of nymphs emerged From each fertile capsule
1.	Ocimum basilicum seeds	0.5	14	13	13
		1.0	14	12	15
2.	Butea monosperm seeds	0.5	08	02	06
		1.0	06	02	07
3.	Butea monosperma flowers	0.5	10	04	07
		1.0	10	04	07
4.	Gynandropsis Gynandra seeds	0.5	14	12	14
		1.0	13	12	15
5.	Acorus calmus rhizome	0.5	08	03	05
		1.0	10	04	08
6.	Control		15	14	15

ANOVA FOR DATA ON FERTILE CAPSULES PRODUCED

S. N.	Source	DF	SS	MS	F	Table 'F' 1% LEVEL
1.	Plant materials	05	910	182	44.3	5.64
2.	Replicates	02	7.81	03.2	0.7	2.56
3.	Error (a)	10	41	4.1		
4.	Doses	01	0.1	0.1	0.07	9.3
5.	Plant materil Vs. doses	05	4.1	0.82	0.58	5.06
6.	Error (b)	12	17	1.4		

ANOVA FOR DATA ON NYMPHS EMERGED

S.N.	Source	DF	SS	MS	F	Table 'F' 1% Level
1.	Plant material	05	563	112.6	13.0	5.64
2.	Replicates	02	34.9	17.4	2.0	2.56
3.	Error (a)	10	86.6	8.6		
4.	Doses	01	12.3	12.3	0.78	9.3
5.	Plant material Vs. doses	05	1.4	0.28	0.2	5.06
6.	Error (b)	10	17	1.4		

roach species fed on treated diets. Of these only a very small number proved fertile. The number of nymphs emerging from these capsules had been very less.

In Periplaneta seeds of Butea monosperma and rhizome of Acorus calamus proved very effective. As compared to normal female, which usually produces 46- 48 capsules, the Acorus and butea- mixed diet fed females produced 8-16 egg capsules, and nymph could emerge from 2-5 capsules only. There was reduction of about 70-80% in the number of nymphs emerging from the capsule of the treated female. The seeds of Ocimum basilicum and Gynandropsis gynandra proved ineffective as there was no difference in the number of fertile capsules produced and also in the number of nymphs emerging out of these capsules.

Similarly, in Supella supellectilium and Blatella germanica also Acorus calamus rhizome and seeds of flowers of Butea monosperma could bring about substantial reduction in the number of fertile capsules produced and also in the number of nymphs emerging out of these capsules.

Results & Discussion:

Acorus calamus in a series of experiments conducted at RRL Jammu is(India) found to affect the ovarian development in Dysders. Acorus (rhizome) has long been valued as an effective anthelmintic and is given in many forms of chronic diarrhoea. In the present study the chemosterilant properties of Acorus calamus rhizome and three other known antehelminthic plant materials: Butea monosperma flowers and seeds, Ocimum basilicum, seeds and Gynandropsis gynandra seeds were screened. The seeds of Ocimum basilicum and Gynandropsis proved ineffective.

Conclusion:

In order to bring about effective management of cockroach populations, a multipronged strategy would prove more effective. This would include:

1. The safe storage of those foods, which are responsible for the higher S.D.I. This would bring about greater mortality and slower rate of development.
2. Use of pesticides and other control measures during weak stages in the life history would enable us to get the maximum result of our investment on the control measures. The early developmental stages in this respect are more susceptible.
3. Use of naturally occurring chemosterilants would bring about reduction in the reproductive capacities of the cockroaches
4. Sanitation is also one of the factors, upon which the abundance of cockroaches depends. Improved sanitation would lower the chances of infestation of cockroaches in the human dwellings.

It is felt that if similar studies are conducted in other parts of the world, we can get some findings to control the problem of cockroach abundance in domestic environment and food industries. The author is very optimistic about this contention.

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